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LANGUAGE AS A CULTURAL CODE: HOW LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES CONTRIBUTES TO INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract. Language as a living organism exists and develops with its people. Similar processes are observed in the cultural code, which is also undergoing irreversible changes. In this regard, an interesting question arises: how does learning foreign languages contribute to intercultural communication and understanding of someone else's cultural code through language, and is language really a cultural code? The purpose of this article is to define the concept of language as a cultural code, as well as to analyze how the cultural code contributes to intercultural communication. In particular, this paper examines the impact of learning foreign languages on the formation of intercultural competence. The authors conducted a survey on the basis of the State University of Management and the National Research Moscow State University of Civil Engineering. The survey results helped to understand how much students are aware of the cultural code and what gaps need to be filled. An analysis of the universities' work programs was carried out, problems were identified and recommendations for their resolution were proposed. The authors concluded that the cultural code includes a language that not only serves as a communication tool, but can also be considered a universal means of expressing any culture.

Keywords: cultural code, foreign language, intercultural communication, education, survey, respondent

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ЯЗЫК КАК КУЛЬТУРНЫЙ КОД: КАК ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ СПОСОБСТВУЕТ МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОЙ КОММУНИКАЦИИ

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Аннотация. Язык как живой организм существует и развивается со своим народом. Аналогичные процессы наблюдаются и в культурном коде, который также претерпевает необратимые изменения. В связи с этим возникает интересный вопрос: как изучение иностранных языков способствует межкультурной коммуникации и пониманию чужого культурного кода через язык, и является ли язык в действительности культурным кодом? Целью данной статьи является определение понятия языка как культурного кода, а также анализ того, как культурный код способствует межкультурной коммуникации. В частности, в данной работе исследуется влияние изучения иностранных языков на формирование межкультурной компетенции. Авторами был проведен опрос на базе государственного университета управления и Национального исследовательского Московского государственного строительного университета. Результаты опроса помогли понять, насколько обучающиеся осведомлены о культурном коде и какие пробелы необходимо заполнить. Был проведен анализ рабочих программ университетов, зафиксированы проблемы и предложены рекомендации для их разрешения. Авторы пришли к выводу, что культурный код включает в себя язык, который не только служит инструментом общения, но и может считаться универсальным средством для выражения любой культуры.

Ключевые слова: культурный код, иностранный язык, межкультурная коммуникация, образование, опрос, респондент

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Introduction

Language exists and evolves with the people who use it, just like a living organism. Throughout the progress of this development, new words appear gradually, some borrowed from other languages, while others fall into disuse and become forgotten. This process takes place with the cultural code, which is moreover undergoing irreversible changes. In light of this, the intriguing question arises as to how foreign language learning contributes to audience interaction and the understanding of another's cultural code by means of language, and if language is a cultural code at all.

Indeed, if we see the daily relevance of intercultural communication, then the ability to establish communication is always of primary importance. It is necessary to be aware then of whether a cultural code does indeed impact intercultural communication, how such an impact occurs, and why knowledge of this matters.

This article aims to define the language as a cultural code, and analyze how the cultural code contributes to intercultural communication. In particular, it examines the influence learning a foreign language may have on the development of intercultural competence.

The cultural code and the functionality of the globalization process in language learning and interaction between cultures is the main focus of this article. The role of language in cultural identity formation and how learning a language enables one to comprehend culturally bound values would also be treated. Inadequate knowledge of a foreign tongue may create certain impediments, which would, in the same breath, be described in this study. The survey conducted in the study will be based on the results of questionnaires filled by students of state management and Moscow State University for Civil Engineering during the years of 1-3 learning. The results will allow us to realize how well-versed the respondents are in these matters, and what knowledge gaps exist and must be filled.

Methodology

The research was conducted using general scientific methods of cognition, while special attention was paid to the systematic analysis of scientific literature on the teaching foreign languages.

A thorough study of state educational standards and work programs of disciplines has shown the need to develop intercultural communication among

students. The standards of the new generation in our country affect the process of integration and rapprochement of cultures, and the issue of finding and maintaining international contacts is being raised. Therefore, modern education is faced with the task of forming intercultural competence. A modern graduate must be able to apply the language they are learning in various fields of cultural, intercultural and professional activity.

Research in this area was conducted by various scientists, both domestic and foreign: S.V. Bobryshov, N.V. Bukina, N.A. Nalgieva, O.L. Petrova, N.G. Tyrnikova, E.N. Shilina, D.G. Estoeva, K. Levi-Strauss, M. Foucault, J. Lacan, J. Derrida and others.

As part of the analysis of the language of the cultural code and its role in promoting intercultural communication, the following methods were used: analysis, conceptualization, comparison and generalization. The survey was conducted on the basis of the State University of Management and the Moscow State University of Civil Engineering. The students were asked anonymously questions about testing their knowledge of language as a cultural code. After collecting the survey results, the data was interpreted. Based on the results obtained, the authors were able to identify shortcomings and formulate recommendations for training.

Discussion

E.N. Shilina, exploring language as the cultural code of the people, says that in the modern world culture no longer has a single center, but consists of many different cultures. The main goal of intercultural learning is the development of tolerance and understanding between peoples. The ability to conduct a dialogue and communicate with other people implies not only the ability to speak, but also the willingness to accept and respect other points of view and cultures. The author notes that cultural consciousness can be considered as a communication skill and gives the following definition: "language is considered as an instrument of group stereotyping of behavior, as a system of encoding and transmitting cultural and semantic information" [6, p. 57].

Based on the author's definition, we understand that with the help of language, people form common ideas and norms. Being a system of signs, symbols and rules, language helps to express your ideas and

thoughts. Language is not just a communication tool, but also an important element that shapes and reflects the social and cultural aspects of human life.

D.G. Estoeva, L.A. Nalgieva and B.A. Mazalievna note that the cultural code contains information "about the features, phenomena, objects that are inherent in a particular ethnic group or people" [3, p. 190]. It follows from this definition that the cultural code includes the language, traditions, values, norms, and history of the country as a whole. All these elements together contribute to mutual understanding and interaction between people, as well as allow them to distinguish their culture from others.

N.V. Bukina in her work presents an analysis of the cultural code through various approaches. The author examines the cultural code through ontological, epistemological, axiological and anthropological approaches. In her opinion, "these approaches make it possible to comprehend the semantic and semiotic expression of the cultural code; this will allow us to talk about the extra- and intrapolar properties of the code in relation to the cultural space, which in turn leads to the idea of considering the cultural code as the language of culture" [2, p. 72].

Thus, it can be concluded that the cultural code is a system through which cultural and semantic information is encoded and transmitted, which allows people to express their ideas and thoughts, as well as interact and understand each other.

The cultural code includes language, which not only serves as a communication tool, but can also be considered a universal means of expressing any culture.

A survey was conducted among students of 1-3 Years at the State University of Management and Moscow State University of Civil Engineering, in which 120 people participated. The purpose of this survey was to determine the level of students' awareness of the concept of cultural code, its impact on the learning process, as well as to find out whether language is a cultural code. In addition, the study considered the need to study the culture of the country in the context of the studied language. The survey results will be presented in the table.

Based on the survey data presented, we draw several conclusions about how students in grades 1-3 understand the cultural code and its relationship to language learning.

For the majority of students, 89% of the language is a cultural code, which indicates a high awareness that language is not just a means of communication, but also a carrier of culture. 81% of respondents consider studying the culture to be important or very important. So, students understand the need of the relationship between language and culture. Among the majority of students, 68% rate their ability to understand cultural contexts at an average level. This may indicate that although they are aware of the importance of the cultural code, they have a need to further develop this ability (this should be taken into account when developing recommendations).

93% of the students believe that language learning contributes to the improvement of intercultural communication, which underlines their confidence that language is a key element in establishing links between cultures. Also, 98 respondents identified language proficiency as the most important aspect for successful intercultural communication. 89% of students agree that learning a language can change their perception of another culture, which indicates that they are open to changes in their worldview.

Regarding language learning methods, the survey showed that 47% of students consider immersion in the language environment and communication with native speakers 37% to be the most effective method for understanding the cultural code. This shows that practical experience and interaction with native speakers play a key role in learning language and culture for modern youth. The main motivations for learning a foreign language are professional prospects (35%) and travel (39%), which indicates the practical application of language skills.

As we can see, the survey results show that students recognize that language is a cultural code, and without understanding culture, it is impossible to fully master the language. They also strive for a deeper understanding of these aspects in their learning.

The next question is how learning foreign languages contributes to intercultural communication. In establishing intercultural communication, two things must be acknowledged. One, it is much broader than linguistic communication. Intercultural communication plays a major role in the learning of foreign languages; by learning a foreign language, one also learns a different culture.

Table. 1 – The Survey

Question	Results
Do you think language is a cultural code?	89 % – Yes 10 % – Not sure 1 % – No
How important is it for you to study the culture of the country together with the language you are studying?	28 % – Really important 53 % – Important 19 % – Not very important
Do you think knowing cultural specifics helps in learning a language?	40 % – Yes, it helps a lot 53 % – Yes, it helps a little. 6 % – No, it doesn't help 1 % – I don't know
What cultural aspects did you encounter while learning a foreign language?	81 of respondents – Traditions and customs 78 of respondents – Literature and art 67 of respondents – History 85 of respondents – Social norms
How do you assess your ability to understand cultural contexts related to the language you are learning?	13 % – High 68 % – Average 12 % – Low 7 % – I don't know
Do you think that learning a language helps improve intercultural communication?	93 % – Yes 7 % – Not sure
Which of the following aspects do you consider the most important for successful intercultural communication?	98 of respondents want to have language proficiency 73 of respondents want to understand cultural differences 1 respondent is interested in other cultures
How do you feel about the idea that learning a language can change your perception of another culture?	20 % – Strongly agree 69 % – Agree 11 % – Disagree
Which language learning method do you consider the most effective for understanding the cultural code?	14 % – Classes with a teacher 2 % – Self-study 37 % – Communication with native speakers 47 % – Immersion in the language environment
What is the biggest motivation for you to learn a foreign language?	35 % – Professional prospects 39 % – Travel 16 % – Socializing with friends and acquaintances 7 % – Interest in culture 1 % – Be able to communicate with a large number of people 1 % – Access to information written in a foreign language 1 % – All of the above

I.G. Belyakova in her work notes the importance of "developing transnational competence, shifting the focus from simple learning of a foreign language to learning the language and culture of other peoples, allowing for critical reflection and

defining boundaries between different behavioral models" [1, p. 65].

Based on the above, students not only practice language, but also develop critical thinking. Shifting the focus from simple language learning to language

learning in the context of culture contributes to understanding the behavior and values of other peoples. This, in turn, helps to define the boundaries between different behavioral patterns, which is important for intercultural communication. Thus, the work of I. G. Belyakova focuses on the need to integrate linguistic and cultural learning.

E.N. Orekhova argues that intercultural communication is the basis for effective teaching of foreign languages. In her opinion, the study of foreign languages cannot be studied outside of culture, just as "the process of communication is impossible outside the context of intercultural interaction, interpenetration and mutual understanding" [4].

Based on the above, we understand that culture shapes language and its use. E. N. Orekhova emphasizes that the successful learning of a foreign language depends on how much attention is paid to the study of the country, its history, in comparison with its own culture. This is how intercultural and interpersonal communication is implemented.

Consequently, language does not exist in a vacuum; it is closely related to the culture, traditions and lifestyle of native speakers. M. V. Rybak notes that in "pedagogy, culture contributes to the formation of personality and has significant educational and educational potential" [5]. This proves once again that language reflects the thinking and values of society, and understanding culture contributes to language learning many times better. It is proved that many expressions in languages have their own cultural references and it is impossible to understand them without knowing the context. This means that "by becoming a participant in intercultural communication, the student must learn to accept a different culture, its values, advantages and advantages. The cultural potential is the strategic objective of the subject "Foreign language"... learning foreign languages must necessarily take place in the context of culture" [5].

We cannot say that today teachers have only one important task – to teach intercultural communication. No, it's not only that. Teachers have been facing this task for decades. However, today there are new opportunities to accomplish this task. Modern technologies are developing every day, which means that learning options are also developing which offer many

language learning opportunities. In addition, neural networks provide a wide range of tools, from chatbots to applications and online courses, which, in turn, opens up new horizons for students.

As part of our survey, the question was asked: "How do you assess your ability to understand cultural contexts related to the language you are learning?" The results showed that only 13% of the students rated their ability as high, while 68% indicated an average level, 12% – low, and 7% – uncertainty in this matter. Due to these results, there is a need to develop strategies and methods aimed at supporting students in improving their understanding of cultural contexts related to the language being studied.

In order to understand cultural contexts, it is necessary to explain to students the meaning and connotation of words, phrases, and stable expressions in the language. For example, there is a difference between house (a physical building that does not carry an emotional burden) and home (associated with comfort, family, security and personal memories). There is a noticeable difference between "I bought a big house" and "East or West – Home is best". Let's also look at the difference between words friend and buddy. A friend is a person with whom you have a strong emotional connection, mutual trust and you value the relationship. Buddy, in turn, is a simple acquaintance, a buddy, without a deep connection. These examples illustrate that words have different shades and it is necessary to take them into account in communication. Taking into account the cultural context, their meaning becomes clear, and the use of such expressions over time occurs on an intuitive level, as a sense of language is formed.

In order to effectively learn a foreign language, students need to take into account the cultural aspect. In this regard, we analyzed two work programs of the discipline "Foreign Language" for various areas of study between the programs of two universities of the State University of Management (GUU) and the Moscow State University of Civil Engineering (MGSU). Both programs emphasize the need to teach business communication in oral and written forms, as in any standard program.

However, a detailed examination of both programs revealed the existence of certain contradictions. For example, in the work program of the training

directorate 27.03.05 "Innovation" the educational program "Technological brokerage" The program focuses on the study of basic historical facts, key personalities, corporate culture, social policy and traditions, as well as issues of corporate governance and personnel policy. An important aspect is intercultural communication, including the specifics of business communication and interaction between representatives of different cultures.

Thus, GUU's educational programs meet the requirements of integrating language and cultural learning, as well as the formation of intercultural communication.

There are two key points in the MGSU work program for the specialty 07.03.01 Architecture: reading and listening comprehension of business and professional information in a foreign language, as well as mastery of the language material. It seems to us that this is not quite complete for learning the language. In modern conditions, it is impossible to ignore the study of culture in the process of learning a language.

Let's take a closer look at the topics that are offered to students. So, students are offered topics such as Baroque Style, Neoclassicism, Eclecticism, Art Nouveau and others, while none of them considers the country of study; only in the topic Architecture of the IX–XVII centuries we noticed a mention of business styles in various countries. It seems to us that this is insufficient.

It is important to note that the lack of emphasis on cultural studies in the process of learning a foreign language can negatively affect the education. Our survey showed that MGSU students are ready for intercultural communication, they want real communication with native speakers, it is important for them to travel and professional growth. We also believe that the study of architecture in MGSU without taking into account cultural aspects can lead to a superficial understanding of the subject, which makes it difficult to apply the knowledge in real projects requiring in-depth analysis and consideration of cultural specificities.

The study of the cultural context contributes to the development of students' intercultural competence through a comparative analysis of cultural characteristics and language systems. Effective foreign language teaching requires the use of modern and interactive methods that take into account current realities, including the impact of digital technologies. Teachers

should effectively use all available educational resources.

An integrative approach that combines language learning with geography, history, traditions, and cultural characteristics contributes to a deeper understanding of the language and culture. The inclusion of topics related to non-verbal communication, cultural holidays and traditions in the educational process, as well as joint watching of films and discussion of literary works, broadens the horizons of students and stimulates independent study.

The low level of students' interest in learning a language on their own (2% according to the survey) highlights the need to develop motivation strategies using available digital resources such as apps, podcasts, and audiovisual materials. According to the respondents, classes with a teacher also proved to be ineffective, because they rated it at 14%.

Insufficient motivation, limited practice, poor teaching quality, and insufficient availability of resources are significant obstacles to effective learning. Unfortunately, a significant number of teachers still adhere to traditional teaching methods focused on mechanical writing and translation, which does not contribute to the immersion of students in the language environment. Moreover, some teachers refuse to use artificial intelligence as a tool to promote the development of their profession. Most educational institutions also do not have the modern resources and equipment necessary for high-quality language learning. All these factors negatively affect the educational process, which in turn makes it difficult to understand the cultural code of the country.

Conclusions

In this article, we have carried out an in-depth analysis of the influence of the cultural code on the process of learning foreign languages and cultural interaction. Consideration of the definition of the cultural code has shown that language, as a carrier of the cultural code, forms a general idea and norms about a particular country.

The conducted research demonstrates that students show significant interest in learning foreign languages, which is reflected in their desire for professional growth and travel. Students also strive for lively interaction with native speakers on equal terms. In this

regard, the task of the teacher is to provide such opportunities. Taking into account cultural peculiarities in the process of learning a language, a future graduate of a higher educational institution will be able to communicate effectively.

The survey results demonstrated that students are actively interested in learning a foreign language in the context of culture, which underlines its relevance and necessity. It is important to take into account the opinion of students when forming curricula.

To improve the quality of teaching, it is necessary to organize additional trainings for teachers, as well as hold different tutorials where experience can be exchanged. It is important to introduce interactive learning approaches such as role-playing and the use of information and communication technologies in the classroom. It is necessary to update the work programs of the disciplines, maintain communication with native speakers and organize clubs where students can practice the language.

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